

Key issues for the design of a German research software institution

General challenges, specific needs and possible solutions

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The German research software ecosystem has systemic deficiencies that impair the quality and reproducibility of scientific results. The FutuRSI project identifies five central challenges based on 18 interviews with experts: lack of development expertise and training pathways for research software engineers (RSEs), insufficient career paths, the heterogeneous structure of the German science system, quality deficits and lack of reusability, and insufficient studies. Ten concrete needs are assigned to these challenges, including long-term maintenance, quality assurance, national infrastructures, training, community services, networking, awareness raising, and institutional legitimacy. Nine implementation formats were identified as solutions, ranging from process support services and governance structures to funding opportunities and career development. The next steps in FutuRSI's conceptualization process include research into comparable institutions and their organizational structures, a risk assessment, as well as the development of concrete participation formats and financing models.

1 Short version

The current research software ecosystem in Germany exhibits systemic deficits that impair the quality and reproducibility of scientific results. In the summer of 2025, the FutuRSi project conducted a total of 18 interviews with experts from the German research software ecosystem using a structured questionnaire to identify general challenges, the associated specific needs, as well as possible solution approaches (implementation formats and instruments).

The interviews reveal five **general challenges** (numbers 1–5). These challenges can be assigned to **specific needs** (letters A–J):

1. Research software is often created **without adequate development expertise**, formal **training pathways** for RSEs are lacking, and **unclear role definitions** between the academic interest in knowledge and the development of research software make it difficult to identify as an RSE or to collaborate between RSEs and other researchers.
 - A. **Education and training:** Develop significantly more training courses, increase awareness of existing offerings, automated and interactive training formats as well as systematic events, build curricula and advance professionalization in the medium term through master's programs or supplementary certificates.
 - B. **Community services:** Establish a central point of contact as a hub and networking node that refers to existing offerings, builds a knowledge base, enables knowledge and technology transfer, provides relief from legal questions and licence decisions, and centrally coordinates access to training resources and links them to established continuing education programs.
2. **Lack and poor visibility of career paths** and **insufficient recognition** for RSEs make recruitment difficult and requires an accompanied cultural change to better appreciate the importance of research software.
 - C. **Awareness building:** Research software must be recognised at all levels as an essential research output and included in review and evaluation processes, which requires persuasion and advocacy with funding organizations and policymakers to establish the development and maintenance of research software as a recognised research activity on par with other research activities.
 - D. **Structural adjustments:** Institutionalise RSE development work, adapt recruitment practices, sharpen RSE profiles, and facilitate career paths through permanent academic positions and project-independent continuity. Furthermore, research proposals should focus more strongly on the reusability of existing software, and funding organisations should explicitly recognize research software development as a fundable activity.
3. The **heterogeneous structure** of the German science system and the **diversity in the research software ecosystem** in Germany complicate unifying activities and differentiation from existing initiatives.

- E. **Coordination/networking:** A coordinating actor should organise the dissemination of successful practices, community building, and working groups, connect to local support, establish minimum standards, and network actors in the research software ecosystem. This actor would also serve as an information multiplier to collect needs and achieve horizontal integration into existing structures.
 - F. **Institutional legitimacy:** A mandated and legitimised actor with a mandate from science policy and the RSE community as an institutional spokesperson and as a recognised advocate for research software concerns to establish corresponding structures in universities, research institutions, and at federal and state levels while ensuring vertical integration at local, regional, national, and international levels.
4. Research software sometimes exhibits **quality deficits** and is often **difficult to reuse** due to lack of publication, discoverability, maintenance, and insufficient knowledge of quality assurance mechanisms.
- G. **Quality definitions and quality assurance:** Develop differentiated quality definitions tailored to specific use cases, disseminate guidelines on quality dimensions and monitor their implementation and usefulness, and enable concrete practical steps to be taken so that software can be better evaluated, published, cited and reused.
 - H. **Infrastructures for research software:** Establish platforms and technical services with a national focus, because international solutions fail due to differing regulations, and local solutions often remain inaccessible, continue to use subject-specific solutions through multiple specialised platforms.
 - I. **Software prioritization and durability:** Establish structured governance to select important research software packages, promote their long-term maintenance and further development, and financially support mature software projects as digital infrastructure to ensure long-term availability and integration of new technologies.
5. **Insufficient research base** on the topic of research software makes it difficult to scientifically assess challenges, needs, and strategic development approaches in the field.
- J. **Research on research software engineering:** Establishing empirical foundations, closing gaps in evidence and promoting the transfer of methods within and across disciplines through trained specialists.

The following **implementation formats and instruments** are mentioned:

1. **Process support services** (e.g., consulting on third-party funding acquisition, documentation, accreditation of local RSE units) are strongly supported, while **development support** through “bookable” RSEs is viewed controversially, as it is personnel-intensive and carries the risk of duplicating local initiatives or recruiting away their

expertise.

2. Existing **training programmes** could be bundled and supplemented by specialised workshops and seminars (e.g., on applications or management competencies) with low barriers to entry, while gaps in the training offering are identified and closed; a multi-level certification system from micro-certificates to complete supplementary certificates as well as the possible accreditation of master's programs in research software engineering could promote **structured skills development** and visibility of RSEs.
3. Low-threshold **thematic funding**, e.g., through a maintenance fund, micro-grants for small projects, and a rapid response fund for acute challenges, could support sustainable software maintenance; fellowship programs, exchange scholarships and sabbaticals for innovations, as well as transfer and spin-off scholarships could also **support outstanding RSEs**, strengthen technology transfer, and establish a network.
4. Measures for **career development** such as webinars, mentoring programs, awards, and a central job board could promote recognition and professionalization of the field as well as increase the attractiveness of RSE career paths in the German research ecosystem.
5. **Community building** through in-person events, workshops, professional community management, and international **networking** could promote exchange of experiences and coordinate local RSE units.
6. A **governance structure** with a broadly accepted mandate could serve as a central **coordinating body** to consolidate findings, coordinate advocacy for research software topics, identify needs, and build strategic partnerships with universities, research institutions, and funding organizations.
7. Continuously updated **guidelines**, directives, checklists, and discipline-specific quality criteria could provide concrete assistance, while a **certification system** with benchmarking suites, peer review communities, and automated quality checks could enable systematic evaluation and assurance of software quality.
8. The development of **technical services** is viewed with restraint, as many central services already exist and proprietary developments are cost-intensive; a **central technical infrastructure** (code repository, web interface for code execution, access to computing services) could be considered in the medium term, but requires careful examination regarding trust, reliability, and coordination with existing providers.
9. **Research on research software engineering** could be established as an independent research area (e.g., on quality, impact measurement, domain-specific requirements), while a knowledge hub with blogs, position and discussion papers, as well as specialised software journals could promote systematic **knowledge transfer** and increase visibility of software publications.

As **next steps** in the FutuRSi project, further research is planned on existing services, offer-

ings, organizational forms, and the development histories of comparable institutions in Germany and abroad. Additionally, a more comprehensive review of the research literature on topics such as quality definition, quality assurance, and sustainability of research software will be conducted. These efforts aim to develop more concrete implementation proposals and make more balanced decisions. The presented implementation formats carry different implementation risks and may compete with existing or emerging solution approaches. Therefore, the project will conduct a systematic assessment of these risks, examine the extent to which established or emerging initiatives reduce or make individual approaches redundant, and analyse possible obstacles and alternative solution paths.

FutuRSi will set up additional participation formats (surveys, webinars, focus groups, digital participation tools) to sharpen the goals and missions of a German research software institution, shape terminology and communication, clarify central strategic questions regarding content orientation, and develop a concept supported by all key stakeholders through identification of additional stakeholders and development of incentive and participation structures. Possible overlaps with existing actors will be examined and redundancies resolved. Potential organizations models will be described and central questions will be discussed and prioritised in a participatory manner to develop options for organizational structures for a possible research software institution. Financing models will be explicitly addressed, examining task-based mixed financing and membership models to evaluate long-term financing options. A sustainability plan will be developed to ensure a permanently viable solution.

2 Starting point and motivation

Research software has now become elementary for digital scientific work and indispensable for the processing of research data. The current research software ecosystem in Germany is characterised by systemic deficits, such as strong fragmentation of knowledge and resources. These deficits impair the quality and reproducibility of scientific results and lead to inefficiencies as well as the loss of valuable expertise. Furthermore, a comprehensive strategy for shaping the research software ecosystem in Germany is currently lacking [1].

The FutuRSi project is conceptualizing a German research software institution [2]. We are helping to shape Germany's future research software ecosystem by facilitating collaboration between research institutions and disciplines, coordinating services and offerings, and strengthening and connecting the people who develop research software. The FutuRSi project involves cooperation between the Society for Research Software (de-RSE e. V.), the German Informatics Society (GI e. V.), the Jülich Research Centre GmbH (FZJ), the Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR e. V.), the Center for Digital Research Competence at the University of Jena (zedif), and the Göttingen State and University Library.

We use the term “research software engineering” as it has a widespread use worldwide. To refer to the people who develop research software, we use the internationally common abbreviation *RSE*¹.

Between July and September 2025, a total of 18 interviews were conducted with experts from the German research software ecosystem. We conducted the survey using a structured questionnaire via virtual communication tools. In this paper, we only present the summary of responses to the following questions²:

- What concrete challenges in sustainable software engineering do you currently observe in Germany³?
- What are the most urgent problems and needs that a research software institution would need to address today³?
- What changes/transformations should the institution bring about in the German RSE landscape?
- What awareness or behavior should specifically change among RSEs/scientists and scientific institutions?

¹ *Research Software Engineer*, plural *RSEs*. The abbreviation we use in this paper should not imply that “RSE” describes an independent identity (which, for example, stands in contrast to an identity as a scientist) or that work as an RSE should not be considered research-oriented (e.g., if one is perceived as a technician). Rather, we assume a diversity of roles in the scientific system, which are fulfilled by people from both the scientific and technical or science-supporting staff in varying degrees. We also address these ambiguities in part when we discuss the inconsistent understanding of roles (see page 7f.). However, an in-depth analysis of designations, self-descriptions, and roles is not the subject of this paper.

² Additional sets of questions dealt in particular with target groups and communication strategy as well as convincing lines of argument and success measurements. The answers to these questions not mentioned here serve the further development of the project and will either be incorporated into our work processes or presented at a later time.

³ With a focus on the federal level, not on the local or international level.

- What specific formats (services, offerings, workshops, certifications, tools, etc.) should the institution provide?
- What form could cooperation between you and such an institution take?
- What first steps would be most important for establishing the institution?

In section 3, we present five general challenges, within which specific needs are listed in grey-highlighted boxes. We address these needs in section 4 and present examples of formats and instruments that can help meet the respective needs. In section 5, we provide an outlook on the next steps in the FutuRSi project.

3 Challenges and needs

This section focuses on the general challenges mentioned in the interviews and the associated specific needs. The challenges and needs mentioned in this section could in principle be addressed simultaneously or sequentially.

The order does not indicate prioritization and does not claim to be comprehensive. Nor do we evaluate the existence or correctness of the description of individual challenges and needs. The enumeration serves in particular to document the responses and is intended to stimulate further discussions about the challenges and needs in the German research software ecosystem.

The interviews reveal five general challenges for the development, further development, and maintenance of research software in Germany: First, there are competency and training gaps among RSEs as well as an inconsistent understanding of what the role or roles of RSEs are. Second, there is a lack of attractive career paths within scientific institutions, a lack of visibility of existing career paths, and a lack of systemic recognition of RSEs by the science system. Third, general science system factors, particularly the heterogeneity of the German federal science system, complicate coordinated or centralizing solution approaches. Fourth, there are challenges with the object of research software itself, for example regarding its quality⁴ and reusability. Fifth, the insufficient research base makes it difficult to assess the challenges and needs.

We supplement the individual challenges with the enumeration of specific needs that relate to the respective challenge and are intended to represent a concrete starting point.

3.1 Competency and training deficits as well as inconsistent role understanding

Competency and training deficits

A large amount of research software is developed without explicit development expertise.

⁴ The aspect “insufficient quality of research software” is frequently mentioned as a challenge, but a general definition of research software quality or a checklist that would allow defining sufficient quality does not currently exist. However, institution- or discipline-specific proposals do exist.

The researcher's necessary methodological knowledge in the field of software development is usually acquired individually, and there is often a lack of formal training pathways for RSEs. Current training courses usually take place locally and/or within specialised communities, are often overbooked, and repeatedly not optimally tailored to specific needs. The situation is exacerbated by the high staff turnover in the academic system, whereby training quality does not remain stable and well-trained personnel leave.

Need A: Education and training

The need for training and qualification offerings is fundamentally very high. Significantly more training courses are needed, increased awareness of existing offerings, and the development of research software engineering education as an independent topic. Automated and interactive training formats should be developed that are supplemented by systematic events and training offerings. Curricula are needed that are built at the master's level at the latest, as well as trainer networks with competency teams for more complex problems. It should be noted that researchers broadly need support to increase the quality of their software engineering. However, this breadth must not lead to neglecting research groups that are capable of developing and possibly also offering research software themselves. The diversity of different course offerings should be maintained, but access should be simplified. In the medium term, professionalization of research software engineering should be pursued, for example through corresponding master's programs or supplementary certificates. However, nationwide regulations are still lacking for this.

Inconsistent role understanding

Work on and with research software has become more complicated with the advancing digital transformation in science, and roles are changing, for example as researchers must cover significantly more areas that are not strictly disciplinary but also technical areas. This creates ambiguities regarding the roles or identities of scientific staff. Some people see themselves solely as researchers, while others, due to the working methods in their respective discipline or research practice, assume a certain dual role. They are both domain researchers and technical developers. Still others see themselves more as "technicians", whose main task is to develop research software and offer it as a service, for example. It is often unclear how the roles between the disciplinary knowledge interest and development can be optimally balanced. The collaboration of staff when these roles are distributed among different people is also sometimes unclear, for example regarding the question of

which tasks should remain in research groups or could be delegated to a central development unit.

Need B: Community services

A central point of contact and networking node for RSEs is needed as a central hub. This should refer to existing offerings and maintain stable contacts. A central aspect could be building a knowledge base as well as knowledge and technology transfer to all scientific end users, for example to provide orientation for access to small high performance computing resources or applications, enable the use of new opportunities through AI technologies, or advise on transfer to industry. End users could thereby be relieved of legal questions and licence decisions. Instead, awareness of these aspects should be created and institutional support ensured so that institutional requirements can be met with minimal effort and evasive movements are avoided. Furthermore, it would be conceivable to centrally coordinate access to training or educational resources and enable connection to established continuing education programs, such as Carpentries, or achieve implementation as part of graduate schools.

3.2 Insufficient career paths and recognition

The role of RSEs in science is not yet sufficiently anchored as a topic. There is a lack of clear career paths, visibility of existing career paths, and adequate recognition for RSEs, as well as a lack of appreciation for the importance of research software for scientific practice in almost all disciplines. Compounding this is the fact that there are hardly any rewards for writing scientific software and competition with industry for specialists is great. Additionally, frequent project financing makes permanent positions for RSEs rare, which makes recruitment difficult.

A cultural change that makes the importance of research software for science widely visible and appreciates the achievements of RSEs as well as the impact of their work on research has begun in approaches but must be accompanied and also co-shaped. This requires a shift in awareness, particularly at the leadership level and in human resources, regarding the role and reputation of RSEs in the research system, but also concrete structural adjustments to address the general challenges of digital transformation in science.

Need C: Awareness building

Research software must be recognised at all levels in scientific institutions as an essential research output and included in review and evaluation processes - and not as a byproduct. This requires persuasion and advocacy with funding organizations and in politics to establish the development and especially also the maintenance of research software as a recognised research activity. In the medium term, the development of research software should be on par with other research activities. To achieve this goal, clear positions on the importance of research software and research software engineering could be formulated and communicated at the leadership level to increase awareness and appreciation. Care should be taken to ensure that RSEs themselves value their work and are happy to identify with their role in the scientific system.

Need D: Structural adjustments

The recognition of development work in the field of research software should be concretely institutionalised and hiring practices should be changed. The profile or role of RSEs should be sharpened depending on the institution or use case, and career paths should be facilitated - in analogy to more established roles such as data engineers who relieve researchers of special tasks. Depending on the problem, permanent scientific positions as scientific staff (less as technician positions) are necessary. Structures for continuity must be created that are not project-dependent. This could also include supporting existing development groups or establishing central units instead of decentralised solutions per faculty.

An open discussion and the provision of resources (specialists, time) in institutions could contribute to improving the framework conditions and culture regarding the roles and career development of RSEs, or regarding possible errors in research software, as well as contribute to structural adjustments at the management level of an institution^a. In research proposals, in turn, there needs to be a stronger focus on the reusability of existing software, possibly as a mandatory evaluation criterion, or also clear guidelines that research software engineering is fundable.

^a As an example, the accompaniment of establishing a CIO position within an institution was mentioned.

3.3 Heterogeneity in the German science system

The German scientific system, in contrast to smaller countries like the Netherlands or more centralised countries like France, is characterised by federalism between the federal states as well as the diversity of science organizations. This makes unifying activities difficult - also because of the sovereign financing of research by the federal states - and complicates outreach to fields not yet reached. In addition, the research software ecosystem consists of a variety of small code projects as well as some large national projects. Furthermore, local and international boundaries as well as boundaries to existing initiatives such as the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) are difficult to draw. Moreover, scientific, science policy, and political committees are not sufficiently explicitly oriented toward research software concerns. Sensitivities in the science system and concerns about the dominance of individual organizations further complicate the situation from the perspective of the experts.

Locally, there are already very successful examples of RSE support with corresponding governance for certain research software, which in particular organise the further development of existing research software. These heterogeneously distributed, sometimes highly specialised and not comprehensively available local RSE units need further support to further increase their performance and possibly open up further. However, a coordinating, legitimate and mandated actor at the federal level is lacking, as well as a central point of entry.

Need E: Coordination/networking

A coordinating actor could work on the areas of community building, organization of working groups, and information dissemination. Instead of central assistance, it could refer to local support, disseminate successful practices, establish minimum standards for software engineering, and network actors in the research software ecosystem, both between institutions and locally among RSEs. As an information multiplier, it could observe initiatives and projects, collect needs and feedback, process them, and disseminate the results further to enable coordinated further development of the field. Important here is creating connecting factors, making differences in the communities visible and balancing them, as well as creating an overview for newcomers. Individual actors should be brought together and good prac-

tices shared, for example with regard to research software engineering itself or also administrative problems in establishing services to support development work. At the same time, hooking own services into a central instance could be enabled^a. A corresponding actor could thus achieve the desirable horizontal integration into existing structures, for example for research data or text publications, and even function as a coordinating funding distributor.

^a Some explicitly advised against building a central, federal RSE pool so that expertise for research software engineering remains local.

Need F: Institutional legitimacy

An actor is needed who is mandated and legitimised to act as an institutional spokesperson for research software concerns in the scientific structure. This should function as a recognised advocate for the topic of research software so that corresponding structures and processes are established in universities, colleges, and research institutions as well as at the federal and state levels. For this, a mandate from science policy and equally from the RSE community is needed. As a contact for politics and community, it must guarantee reliability, build and expand trust, and mediate between national, global, and institutional circumstances. The actor thus guarantees integrated thinking in the research cycle, in particular also the vertical integration of structures and processes at local, regional, national, and international levels as well as interaction with other sectors such as business and administration.

3.4 Insufficient quality and reusability

Quality deficits

Research software often fails to achieve the quality that would be desirable from a researcher's perspective, for example in terms of its architecture. Compared to established standards in software engineering and text publications, there is therefore still room for improvement. Similar to some industrial sectors, ineffective structures also arise in research software that limit testing and maintainability, slow down the training of new RSEs and thus make cognitive and technical enhancements more difficult. In addition, quality measurement proves difficult in practice and is hard to automate. Furthermore, there is a lack of appropriate quality assurance activities such as testing procedures, reviews and

benchmarking in the right measure and for the appropriate use cases. In addition, due to the diversity of research software, a general definition of quality or a comprehensive quality assurance mechanism is unrealistic.

Need G: Quality definitions and quality assurance

To improve software quality, differentiated quality definitions are needed that take into account the scientific use cases and the diversity of research software. In addition, guidelines describing quality dimensions should be disseminated and their implementation and usefulness for specific research pursued. The security evaluation of critical research software should also be advanced. Concrete practical steps are necessary to enable quality assurance, e.g., so that software can ultimately be better published, cited, and thus reused.

Lack of reusability

The reusability and reuse of research software is still often limited. There are problems with dissemination, discoverability, publication, and management of the software. Often knowledge about publication possibilities, principles (such as FAIR4RS [3]), persistent identifiers, metadata, or existing search platforms is lacking. Additionally, software is often not permanently maintained and serviced, which limits its long-term usability. Added to this is the fact that, from the perspective of the experts, organizing software sustainability is primarily an international task that is difficult to integrate into existing funding structures due to national financing structures.

Need H: Infrastructures for research software

National platforms or specific technical services are needed as infrastructure for research software engineering, on the basis of which discipline-specific solutions can emerge. A national focus is more suitable for building such platforms than an international or local approach. The former is too difficult to organise due to specifically national regulations, the latter is often not accessible to outsiders. For this, multiple platforms or services are required for different aspects that enable continued use and reuse. Examples would be “operating systems” for research software, infrastructure offerings, and “research meta-software” such as generators, frameworks, and specialised compilers that better support software engineering.

Need I: Software prioritization and durability

Germany needs a structured governance to select important research software packages and prioritise them for long-term maintenance and further development. Consequently, maintenance of selected software should be supported without favouring only flagship projects. Depending on the level of maturity, important software projects or components should also be able to receive financial support as a type of digital infrastructure, including long-term availability, further development, and integration of new technologies.

3.5 Insufficient research base

In addition to the challenges mentioned above, there is a lack of rigorous scientific, particularly empirical, studies on the use, development and impact of research software. This makes it difficult to assess the systemic deficits, challenges, and associated specific needs. For example, from the perspective of the experts, the concept of sustainability of research software is not yet sufficiently defined. There is also a lack of empirical studies examining the long-term benefits of certain approaches and methods for research software engineering. While these benefits are frequently described in guidelines and position papers, the statements made therein are not always scientifically founded to the desirable extent. This insufficient scientific foundation of existing facts therefore complicates the strategic further development of the field.

Need J: Research on research software engineering

There is a need for dedicated research on research software engineering to close this evidence gap. Research on the topic of research software could provide the necessary insights to systematically create empirical foundations and strengthen the scientific basis for the development of research software in Germany. Furthermore, the specialists trained in this area could advance the transfer of methodologies within and across disciplinary boundaries.

4 Concrete implementation formats and instruments

The answers given by the interviewees in this section provide an overview of possible formats, instruments or mechanisms that could contribute to solving the challenges and needs mentioned in the previous section.

The order does not indicate any prioritisation and does not claim to be exhaustive. We are not yet evaluating the usefulness or feasibility of individual formats. The purpose of listing them is primarily to document the responses and stimulate further discussion about specific implementation formats.

4.1 Support services

Many of the experts surveyed identified comprehensive support services as a key implementation tool for a German research software institution.

Process support services

A process-oriented support service could act as a point of contact and service provider for local RSE units, providing support for specific development tasks, e.g. documentation or metadata maintenance, or searching for research software, thereby potentially reducing the additional workload for RSEs. The range of proposed support services extends from assistance in acquiring third-party funding, to advice on setting up local RSE units or on specific administrative challenges faced by interested institutions, to legal advice on licensing issues and technology transfer. Further procedural support could be designed in such a way that institutions could have their local RSE unit(s) systematically “accredited”. In doing so, different stages of development and specialisations of RSE units should be taken into account, and advice on further development for the renewal of accreditations could be offered. However, the establishment of a generic, central help desk was not recommended due to the heterogeneity of the ecosystem, which is difficult to overview.

Development support

A somewhat controversial proposal involves providing support for the development of specific research software. RSEs could be “booked” to work on individual projects. This would give RSEs trained in a variety of projects the opportunity to transfer ideas from other disciplines. However, some experts believe that this would place too much focus on individual problems, meaning that only a few people would be able to benefit from the support resources. Furthermore, such an offering is significantly more labour-intensive than procedural support. There is also a risk of duplicating local initiatives or even poaching their expertise.

4.2 Training and skills development

Training and continuing education opportunities for end users, as well as raising awareness among students and management staff about topics related to research software, were identified as important measures for capacity building.

Training programmes

In principle, a national institution should bundle and coordinate existing training offerings, supplement them with a central course overview or booking option, and refer to open

e-learning formats. However, experts believe that specialised training offerings based on existing formats such as Carpentries are a useful tool for an institution. In-house offerings could include (half-)day workshops and seminars lasting a few days, which would also include certificates of attendance. These could be application-oriented⁵, or focused on organisational or management skills⁶. In addition, gaps in the training offerings should be identified and closed, duplicate structures should be avoided, and reach should be maximised. All offerings should have low barriers to entry and ideally be conducted virtually, for example, to save travel and accommodation costs.

Structured skills development

In order to increase the visibility of RSEs, some experts advocate the development of a multi-level certification system. This ranges from micro-certification frameworks to full additional certificates for the development of research software. After an initial phase with in-house training courses, a systematic trainer training programme could be implemented. If, after the successful completion of the “Research Software Engineering Master” project⁷, master’s programmes in research software engineering are offered in the near future, it is conceivable that the institution could take over accreditation. In the long term, structured educational resources and formal degrees would be useful, both for master’s students and for doctoral students.

4.3 Funding opportunities

A national institution could offer low-threshold funding opportunities and award grants in the form of material and personnel support, provided that this type of funding is not already adequately covered by the German research funding system.

Thematic funding

A research software maintenance fund, modelled on the UK Software Sustainability Institute (SSI), could support the sustainable maintenance of important software. A microgrant programme modelled on NumFOCUS, which could particularly benefit small research software projects, is also a possibility. Such a programme could be accompanied by a “rapid response fund” that would allow for a quick response to acute challenges, unexpected opportunities or innovation promotion.

Funding for individuals

Fellowship programmes for individuals, such as those offered by the UK SSI and the Netherlands eScienceCenter, can specifically promote outstanding RSEs or development teams, thereby establishing a network of fellows in the short to medium term. A scholarship pro-

⁵ Topics could include AI for the development of research software, CI/CD implementation, test implementation, or good programming practices.

⁶ Expert courses for further training were suggested as a specialised format, for example specialised training courses for developing the technical and leadership skills necessary for successful maintainers.

⁷ See [GitHub project page](#).

gramme for exchange visits abroad (e.g. in relation to specific countries or topics) could strengthen national and international knowledge transfer and collaboration. Another possibility would be a kind of leave of absence to create time and financial resources for innovation (e.g. in the form of an exchange stay or part-time employment). Scholarships for transfer or even for spin-offs could stimulate transfer between science and industry.

4.4 Career development

Measures relating to career development could contribute to greater recognition and professionalisation of the field. They could also increase the attractiveness of career paths in the German research ecosystem by offering prospects for RSEs. For example, webinars for RSEs on specific topics could be tailored to the needs of small and medium-sized enterprises. In addition, a mentoring programme could support individual career development. An annual award ceremony in various categories⁸ or competitive competitions would create recognition for outstanding achievements and increase the visibility of the research software community. Definitions, paths or target positions for job profiles could also be helpful in describing the multitude of existing roles and profiles. In addition, a central job exchange could improve the placement of qualified specialists.

4.5 Community building and networking

Many experts identified connecting with and involving the community as an essential pillar of a research software institution. Respondents emphasised the importance of face-to-face events (conferences, summits, symposia) for exchange and networking activities, but also for disseminating scientific content. Regular workshops and forums with clear added value for participants could be organised to exchange experience and knowledge, for example on research software engineering or to network local RSE units in order to coordinate strategies or simply discuss topics.⁹ Professional community management could also keep the community up to date through newsletters and curated event calendars and refer to teaching materials. International networking plays an equally important role, e.g. to enable a coordinated approach to initiatives or to promote cooperation.

4.6 Governance and coordination

The experts identified governance and strategic coordination as possible building blocks of a research software institution. The aim would be to establish broadly accepted governance with a corresponding mandate, reputation and trust in its services. Within this governance structure, findings could be brought together in a central repository and advocacy (e.g. for planning funds for long-term maintenance) and ownership (e.g. at key events) for topics related to research software could be coordinated. Another governance function could be

⁸ An award is currently being designed as part of the “Research Software Engineering Award” project.

⁹ Other concrete suggestions for networking tools included workshops for exchanging information on the employment of RSEs, an exchange forum for multipliers, a conference on research software research, and a support network for research software maintainers.

to identify needs and initiate appropriate measures to meet them. As a central coordinating body, the institution would establish and maintain strategic partnerships with universities, research institutions and funding organisations. In this way, common ground can be promoted and the involvement of the community ensured through a participatory design.

4.7 Guidelines and certification

In order for research software to be classified as “good” or “high quality”, the experts suggest providing guidelines and establishing a concrete quality assessment system.

Guidelines

The experts suggested that continuously updated guidelines for good development practice, checklists (e.g. for scaling problems or before the end of funding) and guidelines could be provided to offer concrete assistance to RSEs. The establishment and regular review of the effectiveness and usefulness of quality criteria and interoperability standards for research software should be subject-specific and internationally coordinated.

Software certification

For systematic quality assessment, the development of a technical and organisational certification system for research software was proposed¹⁰, which meets defined quality and interoperability standards. Benchmarking suites could be used to carry out a structured evaluation of various quality dimensions, making it possible to systematically close performance gaps with pioneers and flagship projects. Another building block could be the establishment of a “peer review community” that provides a software review service and health checks for repositories¹¹. Badges and automated quality checks of repositories and research software on GitHub/GitLab were mentioned as practical implementation tools. Ideally, quality would then be automatically ensured during the development process so that funding bodies could demand it.

4.8 Technical services and infrastructure

Some experts expressed reservations about the development of technical services. The German research ecosystem already has many existing local and supraregional services. In-house developments are sometimes computationally intensive and therefore costly, so it is conceivable that an institution would simply ensure that technical services provided by partners function correctly. In addition, they require careful consideration of legal and liability issues. Before implementing certain services, it is therefore essential to consult with existing providers.

Individual technical services

Nevertheless, a constantly updated website including API connection should be imple-

¹⁰ However, the usefulness of certification was also questioned.

¹¹ However, it was also suggested that code reviews should be commissioned as needed instead of establishing a service.

mented as a high priority, for example to help find programming courses at local institutions. In order to avoid high start-up costs, it would be possible to offer mature services such as Mattermost/Matrix instances or HedgeDoc notebooks or Overleaf for creating texts. A repository for research software publications was also suggested. A central service overview and the provision of existing tools instead of in-house developments optimises the cost-benefit ratio¹². A research software directory or directory of German research software groups with competence recording and referral services was also identified as useful. Needs analyses could possibly identify special requirements that cannot be implemented at local institutions and could therefore be implemented centrally¹³.

Centralised technical infrastructure

A truly centralised infrastructure could consist of a code repository (“GitLab for Germany”) with public login, a web interface for executing code (“Jupyter for Germany”) and access to internet-based computing services and high-performance computing. In the medium term, this could lead to a kind of “platform engineering” in the field of research software. If this is to be implemented, it should be reviewed beforehand, as such an offer will only be accepted if there is sufficient confidence in the reliability and long-term nature of the service.

4.9 Knowledge transfer and research

From the experts’ point of view, a German research software institute could promote both scientific research and the transfer of knowledge.

Knowledge transfer

A kind of “knowledge hub”, a shared information base that collects knowledge and reports on publications, activities, projects and funding opportunities could support research work¹⁴. A blog reporting on progress in specific research software projects and publishing joint position papers, discussion papers or statements on current topics could systematise knowledge transfer and thus strengthen the institution’s importance in the German science system. A specialised software journal or other forms of software publication could give software publications the recognition they deserve and also contribute to increased searchability and findability.

Research on research software

It was suggested that research on research software engineering should be established and further developed as an independent field of research. Possible topics could include research on the quality of research software, the measurement of impact, and the interactions between technical and social factors. The investigation of domain-specific requirements

¹² Instead of providing central services, it was suggested to create an overview of existing services at strategic partner institutions (such as subject- or institute-specific services) and to promote their use.

¹³ A repository for preconfigured Docker containers was mentioned as an example.

¹⁴ For example, information material on the development of research software based on the information at forschungsdaten.info.

and challenges could lead to innovative solutions and potentially overcome disciplinary boundaries. Regular analyses of the German research software ecosystem and surveys could provide empirical foundations for evidence-based decisions.

5 Outlook

In this section, we provide an overview of the work planned for the near future as part of the FutuRSi project. We would like to point out that we are organising a conceptualisation process with the aim of ensuring that the concept existing at the end of the project period can be implemented directly. As part of the survey, we also received statements on target groups, communication strategy, lines of argumentation and possible measures of success for a research software institution. We will use the responses not reproduced here in the further development of the project, either by incorporating them into our work processes or by reproducing them at a later date.

5.1 Enquiry and analysis

Further research is planned as concrete next steps: On the one hand, we will gather information about existing services and offerings related to research software, and on the other hand, we will compile information about organisational forms and the history of comparable institutions in Germany and abroad. Existing national and international approaches must be identified in order to build on them and see what can be adopted or adapted. In a later step, this should allow us to develop and discuss concrete implementation proposals. Analytically, we will first review the study situation in relation to the above-mentioned requirements in even greater detail. This concerns, for example, topics such as the definition of quality and quality assurance of research software, research on research software, or the sustainability of research software. The results should enable more balanced decisions to be made on the approaches to solving the identified requirements.

5.2 Risk assessment

The implementation formats and instruments presented in the previous section involve different implementation risks and sometimes compete with existing or developing solutions. While some of the formats mentioned already exist in a similar form locally or are being tested in other contexts, others could encounter structural or organisational obstacles that limit their feasibility. In particular, we will examine the extent to which established or parallel initiatives could reduce the necessity of individual approaches documented here or render them superfluous. We will conduct a systematic assessment of these risks and an analysis of possible obstacles and alternative solutions in the further course of the project.

5.3 Community involvement and strategic orientation

Furthermore, we will design and implement additional participation formats and events, in particular to sharpen the goals and missions of a German research software institution. The wishes and needs of the community must be aggregated and aligned with existing resources. We will implement this through various formats and at different levels, e.g. through surveys, webinars, focus groups and digital participation tools. We will publish the results regularly in reports.

Topics could include discussions on how to achieve greater participation or which terms could be adapted or expanded in order to reach as many supporters as possible. Particular attention should be paid to the formulation of terminology and language, as terms such as “research software” or “RSE” possibly do not appeal to all relevant target groups. As a national institution, it should definitely strive for nationwide coverage and provide central components.

Key strategic questions concern the content orientation: Should the institution focus primarily on research software and its quality, or should it also involve the developers and their community? Should it act as a research institution or as a service organisation? As an “institution that shapes”, it could drive forward thematic developments, whereby technical aspects would have to be prioritised over subject-specific approaches. In addition, the institutional focus between universities and non-university research institutions needs to be clarified.

We will identify further stakeholders internally and approach them in various formats. We will develop incentives and participation structures to attract both institutional and individual partners. At a later stage, concrete letters of support will be obtained from interested partner institutions. The overarching goal is to develop a concept for a German research software institution that is supported by all key stakeholders and that also addresses the long-term challenges and needs.

5.4 Organisational models and institutional structure

With regard to a future organisational structure, we will examine possible overlaps with existing actors and work to eliminate redundancies. The independence of an institution for research software could, for example, create better access. In particular, the interaction between de-RSE, GI and a possible research software institution needs to be clarified. First, we will describe ideal organisational models to stimulate discussion about a possible structure. Key questions concern the number of institutions: Is a single institution or are several specialised institutions (e.g. for education vs. other topics) more appropriate?

Another key issue is the question of centralised versus decentralised organisation. We will collect, discuss and weigh up the arguments for a decentralised network of regional centres as opposed to a centralised structure of whatever form. Another topic for debate is whether a virtual or physical institute would make more sense. A physical institute would enable

visits and events on site, while a virtual one is less at odds with the importance of staff mobility today. Legal aspects such as legal form and sponsoring institutions also need to be clarified – perhaps the institution should be affiliated with a university. We will also examine whether individual topics can be addressed first, from which an institution could gradually develop. As a result, we expect to develop options for organisational structures, which we would like to discuss and prioritise in a participatory manner.

5.5 Financing concept

Finally, we will explicitly address which financing model(s) allow(s) for a long-term solution to stabilise the institution/network. A task-based mixed financing model will be considered, in which users (partly) contribute to the financing. Membership models will also be examined. A sustainability plan will present long-term financing options and evaluate various financing models in order to develop a permanently viable solution.

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